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Catalogue of Printed Books. Rules to be observed in preparing and entering titles [18 dicembre 1838] in *Papers relating to the alphabetical catalogue*, London, [ed.] Private and confidential. London, George Woodfall and Son, 1847, p. 79-80. La riproduzione digitale è del progetto Google libri su una copia della Bodleian Library (provenienza British Museum).

CATALOGUE OF PRINTED BOOKS.

RULES TO BE OBSERVED IN PREPARING AND ENTERING TITLES.

- I. Titles to be written on slips, uniform in size.
- II. Titles to be arranged alphabetically, under the surname of the author, whenever it appears in the title, or at the end of the dedication or preface, or in any other part of the work.
- III. In all instances in which variations may be found in the surname, peculiar to the same author, it must be transcribed in that form, language, or peculiar orthography in which it may happen to be expressed in the respective title pages in which it is recorded, as Grange, La Grange, De La Grange; Blanco, Blancus, Le Blanc, De Blanchis, Bianchi, White, etc.; Allciat, Alciato, Alcyot, Alciatus, Alzatus, De Alzate, etc.
- IV. Surnames of noblemen, though not expressed in the title, to be ascertained and written out as the heading of the title.
- V. Christian names, included in brackets, to follow the surname, and all to be written out in full.
- VI. Author's rank in society, in cases in which he enjoyed any eminent honorary distinction, as cardinal, duke, earl, and bishop, comte, baron, baronet, knight, to follow Christian name, and to be underlined. Titles of *inferior rank*, whether ecclesiastical, military, or civil, to be given only when necessary to make a distinction between authors having the same surname and christian name.
- VII. The title of the book next to be written, and that expressed in as few words, and those only of the author, as may be necessary to exhibit to the reader all that the author meant to convey in the titular description of his work.
- VIII. The number of parts, volumes, fasciculi, or whatever may be the peculiar divisions of each author's work, to be next specified.
- IX. Then the form, whether fol., 4to, 8vo, etc.; next the place where the book was printed, and in particular cases, as in the instance of early or very eminent typographers, the *printer's name* may be specified.
- X. The date to follow: when no date or place is specified in the printed book, then either or both may be given, if known to, or conjectured by, the Librarian; but in these instances they must be included in brackets.
- XI. If an early printed book, and in Gothic letters, say in *Lett. Goth.* or *B. L.*
- XII. If printed on vellum or satin, or if an *Editio princeps* of a classical author, or if there are inserted any *Ms. notes*, state these peculiarities.
- XIII. In case of *anonymous works*, some prominent or leading word in the title to be selected as the heading to be prefixed to the title. If the author's name should be known or conjectured by the Librarian, the same to be inserted at the end of the title, and included in brackets.
- XIV. In the case of *pseudonymous publications*, the book to be catalogued

under the author's feigned name; and his real name, if discovered, to be inserted in brackets at the conclusion of the title.

XV. In any long series of printed works, which embrace the collected productions of various writers upon particular subjects, such as Ugolini Thesaurus Antiq. Sacrarum, Gronovii Thesaurus Antiq. Græcarum, the work to be entered under the name of the editor.

XVI. The works of translators to be entered under the name of the original author. The same rule to be observed with respect to the works of commentators, if the same be accompanied with the text complete.

(Signed)

ANTONIO PANIZZI.

18th December, 1838.

No. 47.

[*Addition made by the Trustees to 13th Rule, mentioned in the Secretary's Letter of the 21st of January, 1839.*]

Whenever no leading word can be fixed upon in the title of anonymous writings, the first word in the title, except it be an article or a preposition, may be taken, and the work entered alphabetically under it, adding, however, as many cross-references as may be considered necessary from any other word.

No. 48.

MR. FORSHALL to MR. PANIZZI.

21st January, 1839.

DEAR SIR,—With respect to the 3rd rule, the Trustees wish to know whether it is intended that books should be entered in the Catalogue under the name as expressed in the title page, so that in the first instance given the works of La Grange would be printed in part under each of G, L, and D in your Catalogue.

I am always, &c.

No. 49.

MR. PANIZZI to MR. FORSHALL.

January 22nd, 1839.

DEAR SIR,—I never supposed Mr. Baber to mean that the several works of the same author should be *entered* under different heads, according to the orthographical variations in the writer's name. I understood him to mean that no one but the person who was to superintend the compilation of the Catalogue ought to make any alteration, but leave to this one person to collect the various entries under the one which he should think right to prefer, adding what cross-references he might deem requisite. It is necessary to proceed in this manner, I think, to ensure as much *uniformity* as possible, and I have no doubt Mr. Baber's rule was drawn up for the same purpose.

Believe me, &c.